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Vulnerability Assessment Of Internet Of Thing Systems Using A Classification Model

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ABSTRACT

The exponential growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem has triggered significant cyber security concerns. These concerns stem from various factors, including the heterogeneity of IoT devices, inability to detect novel attacks, and lack of real time detection. Existing approach includes, penetrating testing, fuzz testing and others often struggle with a high false positive and misclassification. In response to this challenges, this study explored classification model .The experimental results demonstrated LightGBM and KNN outperformed other models, achieving a high accuracy of 99%, with precision, recall, and F1 score values of 0.98, 0.99, and 0.98 respectively. These models exhibited exceptional capability in detecting vulnerability while minimizing false positive and false negative, making them ideal for critical cyber security applications .Logistic Regression and SVM also performed well, with accuracy scores of 94% and 93% respectively. However, their slightly lower recall values of 0.90 and 0.89 suggest a potential limitation in identifying all vulnerabilities, which could be a concern in high risk IoT environments. And also while that of Decision Tree (88%) and Neural Networks (86%). The findings show the models have strong detecting capability .future research could focus on integrating explainable AI techniques to enhance transparency and trust in IoT vulnerability assessments.

Keywords; Vulnerability, Machine Learning, Internet of Thing, Classification Model, IOT device. Neural Network

1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet is one of the most important inventions of the last few decades. It has revolutionized long distance communication and how we interact with society. The Internet of Things (IoT) devices have transformed industries and everyday life, the need for enhanced security measures has become increasingly important. The study is aimed to assess the vulnerability of IoT systems using Classification model. Vulnerability in IoT refers to weakness or flaws in devices that can be exploited by attackers. Jabraeil, *et. al.*,(2020). The growth of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), smart sensors, cloud computing, the sixth-generation wireless (6G), and edge computing has significantly enhanced the capability of the Internet of Things (IoT), which is successfully transforming our daily lives through developments such as smart homes, smart cities, Industry 4.0, healthcare, and more (Li *et al.*, 2021). They are now becoming broadly embraced because they offer cost-effectiveness and improve people's quality of life (Arshad *et al.* 2020). According to (Bin Hulayyil *et. al.*, 2023).Most vulnerabilities include poor passwords, insecure services, insecure interfaces, lack of update mechanism, insecure/outdated components, inadequate privacy protection, insecure data transfer/storage, lack of device management, insecure default setting, and lack of physical protection. The complexity of IoT ecosystems, combined

with the absence of standardized security protocols, leaves these systems susceptible to various forms of cyber attacks (Moustafa *et al.*, (2023). By leveraging machine learning, particularly classification algorithms, it is possible to improve the accuracy and speed of vulnerability assessments in IoT environments. Classification models can detect patterns of malicious activity, distinguishing between normal and abnormal behavior in IoT networks (Nisioti *et al.*, (2023). These IoT vulnerabilities arise due to the heterogeneous nature of IoT devices, which often come with limited computational power, weak security. And lack of regular updates.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Framing Research Questions

However framing a research questions is a challenging task. Especially in the field of cyber security, where the scope particularly in vulnerabilities in IoT devices are diverse and complex.

After thorough examination of the literatures the following research questions were framed.

- i. How effective is classification model in analyzing vulnerabilities in IoT systems
- ii. How can classification models be train to identify vulnerability in IoT systems?
- iii. What is the performance of the classification models in detecting vulnerabilities in IoT systems?

Research Design

This study will adopt a research methodology known as Design Science Research (DSR) employed in the field of information models and computer research to solve problems via a problem-solving framework. DSR is a problem-solving paradigm that seeks to enhance human knowledge via the creation of innovative artifacts and the generation of design knowledge (DK) via innovative solutions to real-world problems.

The study utilizes quantitative methods, leveraging existing datasets to develop and evaluate classification algorithms for IoT security. The design is also experimental, as it involves testing various machine learning models to determine their efficacy in identifying vulnerabilities

Figure1.1 Design Research Framework

Model Selection:

The study applies various machine learning classification algorithms for vulnerability assessment. The selected models include: Light GBM, Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Neural Networks, Logistic Regression, and Decision tree

Model Training and Testing:

Each classification model is trained using 80% of the dataset and tested on the remaining 20%. The training data is used to optimize the models, while the testing data provides an unbiased estimate of model performance. Cross-validation techniques (such as k-fold cross-validation) are employed to ensure that the models generalize well to new data.

Model Evaluation:

Once the models are trained, their performance is evaluated using standard classification metrics:

Accuracy: The ratio of correctly predicted instances to the total number of instances.

Precision: The ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of positive predictions.

Recall: The ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of actual positives.

F1-Score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balance between the two.

Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC-AUC) Curve: A metric that evaluates the trade-off between true positive and false positive rates.

These metrics provide a comprehensive view of how well each model identifies Vulnerabilities and distinguishes between normal and malicious IoT traffic.

Table 1. 1; Confusion Matrix

Predicted Class

Positive Prediction	Negative Prediction
True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

T = True, F = False, P = Positive, N =Negative

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

Data Collection:

The dataset used in this study is the Bot-IoT dataset, obtained from the kaggle public repository. It contains 7,062,606 labeled network traffic records and 27 features, representing both normal and malicious IoT traffic. The dataset is widely used in IoT security research for evaluating machine learning models for vulnerability detection, intrusion classification, and anomaly identification.

Data Preprocessing:

Once the data is collected, preprocessing is conducted to ensure it is ready for model training. The preprocessing steps include:

i.**Data Cleaning:** Removing missing or corrupted entries, standardizing data formats, and ensuring uniformity across datasets.

ii.**Normalization:** Ensuring that feature values are scaled appropriately to improve the performance of classification algorithms.

iii.**Feature Selection:** Identifying the most relevant features (e.g., packet size, transmission time, protocol type) that influence vulnerability detection. Techniques like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) may be used to reduce dimensionality and improve model performance.

Classification Model Selection:

The study applies various machine learning classification algorithms for vulnerability assessment. The selected models include: Random Forest, Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Neural Network: Logistic Regression:

Model Training and Testing:

Each classification model is trained using 80% of the dataset and tested on the remaining 20%. The training data is used to optimize the models, while the testing data provides an unbiased estimate of model performance. Cross-validation techniques (such as k-fold cross-validation) are employed to ensure that the models generalize well to new data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data presentation

The Python libraries Numpy, Pandas, Matplotlib, and Seaborn were imported into Jupyter Notebook. Numpy facilitates efficient vectorized computing and broadcasting over arrays with several dimensions. Pandas are advanced and user friendly open-source software for analyzing and manipulating data. It is built on the Python programming language, Matplotlib and Seaborn are Python packages specifically designed for visualizing data. They provide a user-friendly interface for creating visually stunning and useful graphs. Seaborn is built on the foundation of matplotlib and offers somewhat less features compared to matplotlib. The stack program was implemented using python 3.9 in jupyter notebook. The workflow consists of data preprocessing, model training, validation, and evaluation. Each classification algorithm was trained and tested using standard parameters

```
# %%
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sn
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder, StandardScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, learning_curve
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from xgboost import XGBClassifier
from lightgbm import LGBMClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

Fig1.2. importing python libraries

Data Frame

The dataset was loaded into the Pandas data frame for easy analysis, model development, and prediction. The data frame comprises multiple 7062606 rows and 27 columns representing various statistical and signal processing features. The columns include MI_dir_L0.1_weight, MI_dir_L0.1_mean, MI_dir_L0.1_variance, H_L0.1_weight, H_L0.1_mean, H_L0.1_variance, HH_L0.1_weight, HH_L0.1_mean, HH_L0.1_std, HH_L0.1_magnitude, HH_L0.1_radius, HH_L0.1_covariance, HH_L0.1_pcc, HH_jit_L0.1_weight, HH_jit_L0.1_mean, HH_jit_L0.1_variance, HpHp_L0.1_weight, and HpHp_L0.1_covariance. The data types consist entirely of float64, ensuring numerical consistency for further computations biasing them toward majority

Figure1.3.Distribution of Different Attack Categories

Figure1.4. Distribution of Different IOT Devices

Distribution of Labels

Illustration of distributed labels in the dataset, where 0 represents benign traffic and 1 represents malicious traffic.

Figure1.4. Distribution of Labels

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

Comparative Analysis of the Selected Models

The performance of different machine learning models—K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), LightGBM, Decision Tree, and Neural Networks—has been evaluated based on four key metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score. The results, as summarized in the table below, provide a comparative analysis of their effectiveness in classification tasks.

model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
LightGBM	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.98
KNN	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.98
Logistic Regression	0.94	0.92	0.90	0.91
SVM	0.93	0.91	0.89	0.90
Decision Tree	0.88	0.86	0.85	0.85
Neural Network	0.86	0.83	0.82	0.82

Table 1.2 Comparative Records

Accuracy Comparison

Accuracy measures the overall correctness of a model’s predictions. The LightGBM and KNN models achieve the highest accuracy of 99%, demonstrating their strong ability to correctly classify both positive and negative instances. Logistic Regression (94%) and SVM (93%) follow closely behind, indicating their robustness in classification tasks. However, Decision Tree (88%) and Neural Networks (86%) show the lowest accuracy, likely due to over fitting in Decision Trees and sensitivity to feature scaling in Neural Network.

Precision Comparison

Precision measures how many of the predicted positive instances are actually correct, which is crucial when false positives need to be minimized. LightGBM and KNN again lead with 0.98 precision, indicating that they make very few incorrect positive predictions. Logistic Regression (0.92) and SVM (0.91) maintain competitive precision, making them suitable for applications where false positives are costly. Decision Tree (0.86) and Neural Network (0.83) perform the worst in this metric, suggesting they are more prone to misclassifying negative samples as positive.

Recall Comparison

Recall measures the ability of the model to correctly identify all actual positive cases, which is important when false negatives need to be minimized. LightGBM and KNN achieve the highest recall (0.99), ensuring they capture almost all positive cases. Logistic Regression (0.90) and SVM (0.89) follow, indicating a slight trade-off in capturing true positives compared to LightGBM and KNN. Decision Tree (0.85) and KNN (0.82) perform the worst, suggesting that they miss more actual positive cases.

Figure 1.6. Model Performance Radar Chart

The radar chart provides a comparative analysis of different machine learning models—K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), LightGBM, Decision Tree, and Neural Networks—based on key evaluation metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The models demonstrate varying degrees of effectiveness in classification tasks, with some outperforming others across multiple metrics.

CONCLUSION

This study successfully assessed the effectiveness of multiple machine learning models—K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), LightGBM, Decision Tree, and Neural Network—for the vulnerability assessment of IoT systems using a classification model. The

evaluation was conducted using four key performance metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1- score. The results demonstrated that LightGBM and KNN consistently outperformed the other models, achieving superior classification performance across all metrics. Their high recall values indicate their ability to detect vulnerabilities effectively, making them highly suitable for detection. However the LightGBM and KNN models achieve the highest accuracy of 99%, demonstrating their strong ability to correctly classify both positive and negative instances. Logistic Regression (94%) and SVM (93%) follow closely behind, indicating their robustness in classification tasks. However, Decision Tree (88%) and Neural Networks (86%) show the lowest accuracy, likely due to over fitting in Decision Trees and sensitivity to feature scaling in Neural Network.

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